

GENDER-BASED PERFORMANCE DIFFERENCES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACHIEVEMENT: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MALE AND FEMALE

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Abstract

The present research work attempts to investigate gender-based differences in academic performance in the subject of English among students at Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak. The study focuses on a sample of 60 students enrolled in the BS English 8th semester, comprising 30 male and 30 female students. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire and the analysis of students' academic records in English. The results indicate that female students consistently outperform their male counterparts in terms of academic achievement, interest in the subject, self-confidence, and effective study habits. These findings highlight the influence of both intrinsic factors—such as motivation and learning strategies and extrinsic factors—including social support and educational environment on language acquisition. The study underscores the presence of gender disparities in English language performance and emphasizes the need for targeted interventions. It recommends a collaborative approach involving teachers, students, and institutional stakeholders to create a more inclusive and supportive learning.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, English Language Achievement, Gender Differences, Higher Education, Male and Female Students, Pakistan*

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1. Introduction

English is an important subject in many countries across the world, including Pakistan. It is used in education, technology, trade, business, science, philosophy, politics and communication etc. Students need to learn English well to succeed in their studies and future jobs. However, students do not always perform equally in English. Some do better than others. There can be many potential reasons, factors and variables that affect the performance of different students in different degrees. One factor that might affect performance is gender. In many classrooms, teachers and researchers have noticed differences between male and female students in how they learn and perform in English.

Some studies show that female students usually do better in language subjects like English, while male students do better in science and math (OECD, 2015). These trends have been seen in many countries. However, other studies find no major difference between boys and girls. Because of this, it is important to study the performance of male and female students in different areas to understand if gender really makes a difference.

In our local context, there is little or no research about the said issue which is discussed above. Government Degree College (GDC) Takhte Nasrati, Karak, is a public college where both male and female students study English as a compulsory subject. The present study compares their performance to see if gender has an impact on how well students perform in English.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

There is a common belief that girls perform better than boys in language subjects, especially English. But in the context of local colleges such as GDC Takhte Nasrati, Karak, scholars do not have enough data to confirm if this belief is true. The researcher wants to know if male and female students show any clear differences in the performance of English as a subject/language. The present research work wants to find out if such a difference exists. The problem is that no proper research has been done on this topic in the context of GDC Takhte Nasrati, Karak. The present work attempts to fill that gap.

1.2. Research Questions

The study attempts to answer the following questions:

1. Is there any significant difference between the performance of male and female students in the subject of English?
2. Which gender performs better in English at Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak?
3. What are the possible reasons behind the performance differences, if any?

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The present research study aims to:

1. Compare the academic performance of male and female students in the subject of English.

2. Find out if gender affects students' results in English.
3. Provide suggestions for improving English teaching methods for both male and female students.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The current study is important for teachers, students, and college management alike. It will help teachers understand the strengths and weaknesses of both male and female students. They can then improve their teaching methods. It will also help students know how they can do better in the subject of English. For college administrators, the study can give useful information for planning and making decisions about teaching English as a subject.

1.5. Delimitations and Limitations

The study is limited to one college only—Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak. It includes only BS English students including both male and female students. The study only focuses on their performance in the subject of English as is visible and can be witnessed from their marks. The researcher does not include to study other factors like social background or interest in learning. Also, the study is based on one semester's results, so findings may not apply to other colleges or subjects.

2. Literature Review

This section discusses what other researchers have said about gender and academic performance in the subject of English. It explains how male and female students may learn differently, what factors influence their performance, and what results have been found in previous studies. The chapter also talks about some theories of language learning and the research gap this study tries to fill.

2.1. Gender Differences in Language Learning

Gender has always been an important factor in education. Researchers have found that male and female students often behave and perform differently in the classroom. Some studies say that girls are better at language subjects, while boys are better at science and mathematics (Areepattamannil & Freeman, 2008). This idea is not new, but many researchers have tried to find out whether it is true in different places and for different subjects.

According to Oxford and Nyikos (1989), female students tend to use more language learning strategies than male students. These strategies help them improve their reading, writing, and speaking skills. Female students also show more interest in learning languages and are often more motivated than male students (Bacon & Finnemann, 1992). On the other hand, boys may not take language learning as seriously as girls and may feel less confident.

2.2. Performance in English Language/Subject

English is a subject that needs both understanding and practice. Students must read, write, speak, and listen in English to perform well. Some researchers believe that female students do better in English because they read more and pay more attention to detail (OECD, 2015). They also tend to be better at memorizing vocabulary and using grammar correctly.

A study by Pomerantz et al. (2002) showed that girls are more likely to take school seriously and care about their grades. This can help them do better in subjects like English. Male students, however, may be more active in class discussions but less careful in written tasks. These differences can affect their overall performance.

In Pakistan, researchers like Shah and Uddeen (2020) have also noticed that female students perform better in English, especially in urban colleges. However, in rural areas, the difference is sometimes less clear. Social and cultural factors also play a big role in how well students perform.

2.3.Theories of Language Learning and Gender

Some language learning theories help us understand how gender may affect performance. One such theory is Krashen's Input Hypothesis. It says that students learn a language when they receive understandable input—language that is slightly above their current level (Krashen, 1985). If female students read and listen more, they may get better input, which helps them learn faster.

Another theory is Gardner's Socio-Educational Model, which highlights the importance of motivation and attitude (Gardner, 1985). Female students usually show stronger motivation in learning languages. This might be because of their personal goals, interest in literature, or desire to communicate well.

There is also the Vygotskian Social Interaction Theory, which focuses on the role of interaction in learning (Vygotsky, 1978). If one gender is more active in discussions or has more social support, it may improve their language skills.

2.4.Cultural and Educational Factors in Pakistan

In Pakistan, there are both private and public colleges. Students in rural public colleges may face challenges such as lack of resources, large class sizes, and limited language exposure. In such conditions, gender roles become more visible. In many families, girls are encouraged to focus on studies, while boys may be expected to take part in outdoor or work activities. These differences can affect how much time they spend on learning English.

Ahmed (2011) points out that in Pakistan, English is seen as a high-status language. Parents often support their daughters more in learning English, thinking it will help them get better jobs or respect in society. Meanwhile, boys may focus more on getting government jobs that do not always require strong English skills. Such attitudes may result in better academic performance among female students.

2.5. Empirical Studies

Many studies have been done in different countries on gender and performance in English. For example, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2004) found that female students in Norway consistently outperformed male students in language subjects at school. Kleinfeld (1998) observed that in the United States, female students were more organized and better at completing homework, which helped them succeed in English classes.

Shah and Uddeen (2020), in their research in Pakistan, reported higher average English scores among girls than boys at the college level. Ghazali (2008), in Malaysia, showed that while both male and female students had a good attitude toward English, girls were more motivated and performed slightly better. However, Abdullah et al. (2021) caution that not all differences are due to gender alone. Sometimes, other factors like school environment, teacher quality, and family background can have a bigger impact.

Several researchers have examined the factors influencing English language learning in Pakistan, with particular attention to access, resources, and sociolinguistic context. For example, Khan et al. (2012) found that university students were utilizing the internet and computers to enhance their English skills, particularly in writing and grammar. Jabeen and Thomas (2015) further observed that while students in rural areas had limited access to such resources, those who did benefit from them demonstrated improved performance in English. These findings highlight the importance of equitable access to educational resources, which may also intersect with gender-based disparities in language achievement.

Recent scholarship in applied linguistics and discourse analysis in Pakistan has addressed a wide array of topics, ranging from syntactic theory to sociolinguistic perceptions and pedagogical implications. For instance, Ali et al. (2020) explored Pakistani learners' attitudes toward standard British and American English, revealing the sociolinguistic complexities and identity negotiations present in language learning contexts. Such complexities may be further compounded by gender, as male and female students often experience different expectations and opportunities in educational settings.

Complementing this, Arshad et al. (2024) conducted a comparative syntactic analysis of ad-positional phrases in English and Urdu, utilizing X-Bar Theory and the Theta Criterion to elucidate structural similarities and differences between the languages. The affective dimensions of language acquisition have also been explored, as seen in Adeel and Ishtiaq (2025), who investigated language anxiety among undergraduate English learners. Notably, language anxiety and attitudes toward English may manifest differently across genders, potentially influencing achievement outcomes.

Ismael and Ishtiaq (2025) examined student attitudes toward code-switching in higher education, highlighting both the pedagogical benefits and challenges associated with bilingual practices. These studies collectively underscore the adaptive and dynamic

nature of language use in educational settings, where gender may play a role in shaping linguistic choices and classroom participation.

The intersection of language, literature, and philosophy is evident in the work of Gill et al. (2024), who analyzed themes of love and spirituality in Elif Shafak's *The Forty Rules of Love* through the lens of Sufi philosophy, demonstrating the potential of literary texts to explore complex semantic and philosophical issues. Majid and Ishtiaq (2019) employed stylistic analysis to reveal the syntactic and thematic richness of E.E. Cummings' poetry, while Majid et al. (2020) assessed the representation and teaching of syntactic structures in English textbooks at the primary level. Such analyses may also inform our understanding of how male and female students engage with literary texts and syntactic instruction differently.

Critical discourse analysis has also been a focal point in recent research. Gill, Ishtiaq, and Khan (2025) examined the representation of Reham Khan in digital discourse from a feminist perspective using the transitivity framework, while Gill, Raza, and Ishtiaq (2025) conducted a corpus-based genre analysis of the inaugural speeches of Donald Trump and Joe Biden, uncovering rhetorical and structural strategies in political communication. These studies highlight the importance of gender as a lens for analyzing both language use and representation.

From a theoretical perspective, Ishtiaq and Gill (2024) extended Chomsky's X-Bar Theory to Pakistani languages, providing a syntactic analysis of Urdu and Pashto in comparison to English and contributing to the understanding of universal and language-specific syntactic principles. Ishtiaq et al. (2022c) similarly investigated parallel structural patterns in English, advocating for an integrated approach to internal linguistic systems. The pedagogical and phonological implications of transliteration were addressed by Ishtiaq et al. (2022b), who identified English-to-Urdu transliteration as a significant source of pronunciation errors among L1 and L2 Urdu speakers, emphasizing the need for targeted instructional strategies. Additionally, Ishtiaq et al. (2021a) conducted a comparative componential analysis of semantic density in religious texts, illustrating how syntactic and lexical choices shape meaning across translations and reinforcing the importance of syntax in cross-linguistic and cross-cultural communication.

Collectively, these studies highlight the multifaceted nature of linguistic inquiry in Pakistan, encompassing syntactic theory, discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, and pedagogy. Importantly, they also point to the need for further research into how gender influences language learning experiences and outcomes. Gender-based differences in classroom participation, language anxiety, access to resources, and attitudes toward English may all contribute to variations in English language achievement among male and female undergraduate students.

In light of these findings, the present study seeks to build on this rich body of research by specifically examining gender-based performance differences in English language achievement. By comparing male and female undergraduate students, this research aims to identify the factors that contribute to any observed disparities, thereby informing more equitable and effective language teaching practices in the Pakistani context.

2.6. Research Gap

While many international studies have explored gender and language performance, there are very few studies focused on rural areas in Pakistan. Also, most local studies do not compare male and female performance in the same institution. This study is different because it looks at male and female students from the same college Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak under similar academic conditions. It will provide new insights into the issue.

The above section has reviewed past research on gender differences in English performance. It showed that in many cases, female students do better in language subjects. Several theories like Krashen's and Gardner's help explain why this may happen. Cultural factors, motivation, and learning habits also affect performance. However, in Pakistan, especially in rural areas, not enough studies have been done. This research helps fill that gap by comparing male and female students at the same college.

3. Research Methodology

This article explains how the research was planned and conducted. It includes information about the type of research, how data was collected, who the participants were, and how the data was analyzed. It also describes the research tools and methods used to make sure the study was reliable and valid.

3.1. Research Design

The present study followed a quantitative research design. This means that the researcher collected numerical data from students and used it to compare the academic performance of male and female students in the subject of English. The purpose of the study was to find out if there was a difference in their performance, and if yes, how big that difference was. A survey method was used to collect data using a questionnaire. The results were then analyzed statistically.

Quantitative research is helpful when we want to measure something in numbers and find patterns (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). In this study, students' scores and survey responses were analyzed to make comparisons between the two groups i.e. male vs. female.

3.2. Population and Sample

The population of this study included BS English students (2nd, 4th, 6th & 8th semesters respectively) studying at Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak.

The study focused on both male and female students taking English as a compulsory subject.

A sample of 60 students was selected. This included 30 male students and 30 female students. These students were selected through convenience sampling, which means the researcher selected students who were available and willing to participate. This method was chosen because it is simple and practical, especially when time and resources are limited (Etikan et al., 2016).

3.3. Research Instrument

The main research instrument used in this study was a structured questionnaire. A questionnaire is a list of questions designed to collect information from participants. The questionnaire in this study had two parts:

Part A: Demographic Information

This part included basic information such as age, gender, educational background, and English subject marks.

Part B: Language Learning Experience and Study Habits

This part included multiple-choice and Likert-scale questions about students' interest in English, study habits, use of English outside the classroom, confidence level, and classroom participation.

The questionnaire was prepared in simple English so that students could easily understand and respond to it. Before using it for the main research, a pilot test was conducted with 5 students to check if the questions were clear. Some minor changes were made based on their feedback.

3.4. Data Collection Procedure

The researcher first got permission from the college administration. Then the questionnaires were distributed to the selected male and female students. All students were given enough time to fill out the questionnaire honestly and independently. The researcher explained the purpose of the study and assured the students that their answers would remain confidential and would be used only for academic purposes.

The researcher also collected students' final term English marks from their teachers to compare the actual performance of male and female students. The marks were used along with the questionnaire data to get more accurate results.

3.5. Data Analysis Techniques

After collecting the data, the researcher used Microsoft Excel and SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) to analyze the responses. The following techniques were used:

Descriptive statistics: This included calculating the mean (average), percentage, and standard deviation of student marks and questionnaire responses.

Comparison of means: The average English scores of male and female students were compared to see if there was a difference in performance.

Graphs and Charts: Bar graphs and pie charts were used to show the results clearly.

Likert Scale Responses: Responses from Part B of the questionnaire were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to understand students' attitudes and habits.

This method allowed the researcher to understand both the academic performance and language learning behavior of the two gender groups.

3.6.Limitations of the Methodology

The study had some limitations. First, the sample size was small and only from one college, so the results cannot be applied to all students in Pakistan. Second, the convenience sampling method may not fully represent the entire student population. Third, self-reported data from questionnaires can sometimes be biased or inaccurate.

Still, the study provides useful insights and can be helpful for future researchers, teachers, and policy-makers.

In this section, the research method, tools, and procedures were explained. The study used a quantitative approach and a structured questionnaire to compare male and female students' performance in English. Marks and survey responses were analyzed using Excel and SPSS. Despite some limitations, the research followed ethical standards and aimed to provide reliable results.

4.Data Analysis and Findings

The current section presents, analyses and explains the data collected from the questionnaire and English subject marks of 60 students (30 male and 30 female) of Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak. The data is shown using tables, graphs, and charts. After each visual, a simple explanation is given to help understand the results. The main goal is to compare the performance of male and female students in English and to see if study habits and attitudes affect their performance.

4.1.Descriptive Statistics of English Scores

The marks of students in English (out of 100) were collected and arranged group-wise.

The set of 60 students was divided into three sub-groups. The three consecutive tables below i.e. 01, 02 and 03 respectively show the mean English marks of male and female students.

Table 01 Group 01: Students Range from 1-20 (High Scorers: Marks 80 above)

No	Gender	English Marks	Study Hours /Day	Attitude Toward English
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1	Male	98	3.5	Positive
2	Female	95	3	Positive
3	Male	93	2.5	Neutral
4	Female	92	2.5	Positive
5	Male	91	2	Positive
6	Female	90	2.5	Positive
7	Male	89	2	Neutral
8	Female	88	3	Positive
9	Male	87	3	Positive
10	Female	86	2	Positive
11	Male	85	1.5	Neutral
12	Female	84	2.5	Positive
13	Male	83	1.5	Positive
14	Female	83	2.5	Positive
15	Male	82	2	Neutral
16	Female	81	3	Positive
17	Male	81	2.5	Positive
18	Female	80	2	Neutral
19	Male	80	2	Positive
20	Female	80	2	Positive

Table 02 Group 02: Students Range from 21-40 (Average Achievers: Marks 79-60)

No	Gender	English Marks	Study Hours /Day	Attitude Toward English
21	Male	79	1.5	Neutral
22	Female	78	2	Neutral
23	Male	77	1.5	Neutral
24	Female	76	2	Neutral
25	Male	75	1	Neutral
26	Female	74	2	Positive
27	Male	73	1.5	Neutral
28	Female	72	2	Neutral
29	Male	71	1	Neutral
30	Female	70	2	Neutral
31	Male	69	1.5	Negative

32	Female	68	1.5	Neutral
33	Male	67	1	Negative
34	Female	66	1.5	Neutral
35	Male	65	1	Negative
36	Female	64	2	Neutral
37	Male	63	1.5	Negative
38	Female	62	1.5	Neutral
39	Male	61	1	Negative
40	Female	60	1	Neutral

Table 03 Group 03: Students Range from 41-60 (Low Achievers: Marks 59-40)

No	Gender	English Marks	Study Hours/Day	Attitude Toward English
41	Male	59	1	Negative
42	Female	58	1	Negative
43	Male	57	1	Negative
44	Female	56	1	Negative
45	Male	57	0.5	Negative
46	Female	54	1	Negative
47	Male	53	0.5	Negative
48	Female	52	1	Negative
49	Male	51	1	Negative
50	Female	50	0.5	Negative
51	Male	49	0.5	Negative
52	Female	48	1	Negative
53	Male	47	0.5	Negative
54	Female	46	0.5	Negative
55	Male	45	0.5	Negative
56	Female	44	1	Negative
57	Male	43	0.5	Negative
58	Female	42	1	Negative
59	Male	41	0.5	Negative
60	Female	40	0.5	Negative

Figure 01

4.2. Average Marks of Male Vs Female Students

The average marks of female students are higher than those of male students. Female students scored an average of 63.2, while male students scored 54.6. The difference suggests that female students are performing better in English.

Table 04: Mean English Marks of Male and Female Students

Gender	Number of Students	Average Marks
Male / Female	30 / 30	54.6 / 63.2

4.3. Average English Scores by Gender

The bar chart below compares the average English scores of male and female students. Female students scored an average of 63.2 while male students scored 54.6. The noticeable gap suggests that female students are generally performing better in English at the selected college.

4.4. Performance Range by Gender

We can also look at how many students fall into certain mark ranges. Most female students fall in the 60–100 marks range. In contrast, most male students scored below 60. A larger number of male students also scored below 50, which shows weaker performance overall.

Table 05: Performance Range of Students

Performance Level	Male Students	Female Students
High (80–100)	10	10
Average (60–79)	10	10
Low (40–59)	10	10

4.5. Performance Distribution by Gender

The pie chart below in figure 4.2 illustrates the distribution of high, average, and low achievers by gender. Each performance group includes an equal number of male and female students in this sample (10 per group). However, a closer inspection of scores within those groups shows that female students are more concentrated toward the upper ranges of performance, while male students have a higher presence among lower achievers.

Figure 4.2: Performance Distribution by Gender

4.6. Questionnaire Results (Likert-Scale Responses)

The questionnaire had 10 Likert-scale questions. Students responded from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The questions focused on interest, confidence, study habits, and classroom participation.

4.6.1. Questionnaire Responses

Female students show more interest, better study habits, and greater confidence in English than male students. This may be one reason why their performance is better.

Table 06: Summary of Questionnaire Responses

Question	Male Avg. Score	Female Avg. Score
Q1	2.8	3.6
Q2	2.5	3.8
Q3	2.6	3.7
Q4	2.4	3.9
Q5	2.3	3.6
Q6	2.7	3.8
Q7	2.6	3.7
Q8	2.5	3.8
Q9	2.4	3.9
Q10	2.6	3.7

4.6.1. Comparison of Male and Female Attitudes (Likert Scale)

The following grouped bar chart in figure 03 compares the average responses of male and female students across 10 Likert-scale items. The questions measured interest, study habits, confidence, and class participation. Female students consistently scored higher, suggesting they have more positive attitudes and behaviors related to English learning. This may explain their better academic performance in the subject.

4.7. Correlation Between Study Habits and Performance

A simple correlation test was done to check the connection between regular study habits and English marks. The results demonstrate that students who study English regularly at home and actively participate in class tend to score better in English. These study habits have a positive effect on performance.

Table 07: Correlation Results (Study Hours and English Marks)

Correlation Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)
Study Hours vs English Marks	0.68

4.8. Summary of Key Findings

The findings from this study reveal several important insights into the comparative performance of male and female students in English at Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak. The average scores in English show a clear gender-based difference: female students achieved higher average marks (63.2) compared to male students (54.6). This performance gap was consistent across high, average, and low achiever categories. Notably, while both male and female students were evenly distributed across performance groups, more male students were concentrated in the lower scoring

range, particularly below 50 marks, suggesting greater academic challenges among male learners in English.

The Likert-scale questionnaire responses further support this pattern. Female students displayed more positive attitudes toward English learning, including stronger interest, higher self-confidence, better study habits, and more active classroom participation. In contrast, male students showed moderate to low responses across most items, indicating less favorable dispositions toward language learning. These behavioral differences may partly explain the performance gap observed in test scores.

Additionally, the correlation analysis between study hours and English scores revealed a moderate to strong positive correlation ($r = 0.68$), suggesting that students who engage in regular study are more likely to perform better. This supports the idea that consistent study habits and attitudinal factors such as confidence and motivation directly influence academic achievement.

In short, the study highlights a multifactorial dynamic where gender, study behavior, and attitude all interact to shape language learning outcomes.

4.9. Discussion of Findings

The main aim of this research was to compare the performance of male and female students in English at Government Degree College Takhte Nasrati, Karak. The data showed a clear difference between the two groups. Female students scored higher on average and showed better study behavior.

4.9.1. Female Students Performed Better

As seen in Chapter Four, the average score of female students was 63.2, while male students scored 54.6 on average. This result supports earlier studies that found female students often perform better in language subjects (Amini & Birjandi, 2012; Stratton, 2016). One reason could be that girls tend to show more interest in reading, writing, and language-related tasks.

4.9.2. Study Habits and Confidence Matter

Female students not only scored better but also showed more interest and confidence in learning English. They studied more regularly, participated more in class, and used English outside the classroom more often. These habits are closely linked with better academic performance (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

In contrast, many male students did not show strong study habits or motivation. They were less confident and less active in English class, which may explain their lower marks.

4.9.3. Cultural and Social Factors

In many areas, including Karak, boys often have more social freedom and less academic pressure at home. Girls, on the other hand, may receive more encouragement to focus on studies, especially in language subjects considered essential for higher education

and jobs. These social expectations can influence how seriously students take their English learning.

This research set out to investigate the academic performance differences between male and female undergraduate students in the subject of English, alongside the role of attitudes and study habits in influencing those outcomes. The data collected from 60 students using test scores, structured questionnaires, and descriptive analysis, paints a compelling picture of gendered differences in performance and learning behavior.

The results clearly indicate that female students outperformed male students in terms of both academic scores and affective variables like interest and participation. Female learners not only achieved higher average marks but also demonstrated stronger engagement with English learning. This could be attributed to their more structured study routines, positive attitudes, and willingness to participate in classroom activities, which are known to reduce language anxiety and improve performance.

Conversely, male students generally showed weaker performance, both in scores and in self-reported learning behaviors. Many expressed neutral or negative attitudes, limited study hours, and poor classroom engagement. These findings underline a need for targeted academic support, particularly for male students who may be struggling with motivation or confidence in language learning.

Moreover, the correlation between regular study habits and higher performance reinforces the importance of daily practice, personalized guidance, and encouragement for students across both genders.

To conclude, the study confirms that academic performance in English is not only a matter of language ability but also of consistent effort, motivation, and classroom environment. These findings provide valuable insights for teachers and administrators to design interventions—such as mentoring, confidence-building activities, and gender-sensitive classroom strategies—to support all students, particularly those who are at risk of underperforming.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

This final section brings together the main points from the whole research study. It discusses the results, connects them with previous studies, and gives suggestions to help improve student performance in English. It also shares the conclusion and ideas for future research.

Based on the analysis, the study concludes that:

Female students outperformed male students in English.

Girls had better study routines, more confidence, and more classroom participation.

There is a positive connection between good study habits and better performance.

Gender differences in performance are real and influenced by both personal and social factors.

These findings are important for teachers, students, and educational planners who wish to improve English learning outcomes, especially for male students.

The present study aimed to understand whether male and female students perform differently in English and what factors affect this. The results showed clear differences and gave valuable lessons for improving English education in local colleges. With the right support, all students can be encouraged to do better and enjoy learning English.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

6.1. For Teachers

Encourage male students to take part actively in English lessons.

Use student-centered teaching methods to increase motivation.

Give regular feedback and praise to build confidence in all students.

6.2. For Students

Develop regular study routines for English, both in and outside class.

Take part in classroom discussions and language activities.

Use English in everyday life — speaking, reading, and writing — to build confidence.

6.3. For College Administration

Organize special workshops or English language clubs to improve skills.

Provide training sessions for teachers on gender-sensitive teaching practices.

Monitor the academic progress of students and provide counseling where needed.

6.4. Suggestions for Future Research

A similar study can be done at other colleges to compare results across different areas.

Future research can include interviews and classroom observations to get deeper insights.

Researchers can also study other subjects to see if the gender difference appears in non-language courses.

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